
Introspecting the Antecedents of Changing Dynamics in Talent Acquisition and Talent Management

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Abstract

Talent Acquisition and Talent Management are very critical to any organization. Technology has paved way for innovative methodologies in the otherwise traditional approaches in these processes. In order to understand the modern dynamics of these processes an in depth analysis needs to be conducted and identify the prevailing antecedents for the same. The paper attempts to study the traditional and the modern disruptive talent acquisition process, identify the influence of modern factors on changing dynamics of talent acquisition and finally understand the impact of culture, technology, quality of hire and Leadership on Job Retention. SPSS 20 was used for analyzing the impact of these antecedents and develop a proposed model in order to study the individual influence of each of the variables. Leadership, Technology and Culture all were found to be having a non- significant impact towards job retention, whereas Quality of hire was the only factor that significantly impacted job retention. The findings of the study clearly depict that emphasis is more on the quality of the employees hired as compared to other antecedents. Hence it is important for the organizations to have strategies in place for attracting and managing a quality employee for achieving the goal of job retention.

INTRODUCTION:

Talent acquisition helps in shaping the perception of employers in the market and is very dynamic in nature. The process is extremely critical as talent acquisition strategies are important especially for those companies who fail to find right skilled employees. On the other hand talent management comprises of utilizing the strategic human resource leading to enhancing the business value and helping the organizations their business goals. Innovative and dynamic organizational are using the innovative methodologies to harness the best available talent pools. Globalisation has further emerged as a major challenge in redefining the hiring landscape. As per the annual Global CEO survey study done by PwC in the year 2014, the study suggests that companies are preparing hard to implement innovative strategies in their firms (PwC, 2014). UK Department of Business Innovation and publication has argued that governments all over the world are in the favor of sponsoring and promoting innovative designs catering to modern technology. Governments all over world are also in support of promoting

and sponsoring innovating design and ideas. The advent of big data gives rise to complex data sets and the results have shown that new generation millennial are not interested in the traditional definition of professional careers, work, peer to peer collaborative communities. The increasing attrition rates also has been a major challenge with most of the organisations. As stated by Huselid (1995) human resource plays a significant role in augmenting the performance of an organization and effectiveness. Hence it becomes even more important for the organizations to consistently evolve towards attracting the best available talents in the market. In order to leverage competitive advantage and performance management talent plays a major role as differentiator (Bhatnagar, 2004).

Organisations having good strategy of talent acquisition and management can definitely boast of better employee engagement and enhanced productivity.

Fig.1 Talent Acquisition and management (Ronn, 2007)

A good talent acquisition and management process that is rightly defined and stated from end to end process will be well executed. It will also result in consistency in the application and will comply with all the prerequisite requirements that will help the organisations achieve the competitive advantage in the talent acquisition and management zone(Ronn, 2007) as shown in fig 1.

Talent acquisition- What it actually is?

Fig. 2 Strategic Elements of talent Acquisition and Management

The strategic elements of talent acquisition and management are inclusive of various other parameters. From the fig.2 it is evident that talent acquisition and planning is one of the most important strategy that guarantees alignment of business, inspects the various workforce plan in place along with covering for global considerations. Workforce segmentation ensures that there is a thorough understanding of various categories of workforce and their segments. This also segregates the various positions associated with these workforce segments, skillsets required and competencies needed for achieving success. Another important highlight is the employment branding. This helps in uncovering and defining the organizational culture and image of the company. Identification of key differentiators, reputation of the organization, quality of hire and products and services as delivered by the organization is also major focus of consideration. Defining the right candidate audience is another important element as it helps in identifying the right source to acquire right talent for specific roles. Providing positive outlook and experience to candidate, understanding the various dimensions of candidate community and managing the association with those candidates that are not selected is also an important part of talent acquisition and management. Finally the technology aspect that caters to the understanding of metrics and analytics related to recruitments and gaining insights from those measurements for continuously improving the process so as to make better recruiting decisions will eventually lead to improved quality of hire.

Understanding the Talent Management Theory

According to Miner, (1973) talent management can be broadly defined as the one the most important HR process that is specifically designed for top management positions and is more focused towards drawing and choosing from the most intellectually suitable talent. It also aims at recognizing and evaluating the successful characteristics of a specific individual.

Another common argument proposed by Collings and Mellahi, (2009) states that talent management is the process that involves activities primarily focused on identifying the key areas that have substantial contribution towards achieving the organizational objectives and goals. The process also involves overall development of the identified talent pool comprising of the high performers and orient them towards a differentiated human resource architecture within the organization so that they are continuously committed towards the organization. Concept of global talent management also comes into picture with major focus being incorporation of global dimensions that includes initiatives such as attracting, selecting, developing, and keeping the best employees in the most important roles worldwide (Vaiman, Scullion, and Collings 2012).

In a study conducted by Stahl et al. (2012), where they have selected organizations that boasts of high performance oriented and have good reputation as employers. Two categories were identified towards understanding talent management. Differentiated approach that cater to limited high potential; employees and inclusive approach that was made available to the employees. It was noteworthy to know that findings clearly stated that organisations do not merely copy existing practices of other top performing companies but they must try to bring a level of alignment in terms of their existing practices, strategies and values. As depicted in the fig.3 six principals of achieving global talent management were highlightes in the study.

Fig 3 Principals of achieving global talent management (Stahl et al. 2012)

Talent management theories have always stressed on the assumptions stating the importance of maximizing the employees' talent being the single most important source for gaining competitive advantage (Scullion et al., 2010). As a result of this talent management has been directly related human resource management practices of an organization aiming at increased business performances (Farndale, Scullion, & Sparrow, 2010). Talent is a very subjective term that requires an undisputed understanding within the HR managers and top management firms as well as they may have different perspectives towards various sources of attaining competitive advantage for the organization. The challenge faced by most of the organisations is the attracting, assessing, training and retaining the talented pool of employees. Hence the organisations can try to identify the existing pool of talent and focus on developing them rather than trying acquire new talent that might lead to exaggerated costs involved.

Major disruptions are observed in the process of talent acquisition and management due to intrusion of technology in the process of hiring. Organisations have been constantly being challenged by social networks, aggressive marketing by the competitor's brands and re-recruitment of employees every day. The catch here is to understand and select the most suitable technology that will reach right kind of talent and develop a well-planned talent recruitment process aligning organizational goals and objectives.

Hence the present study attempts to understand the traditional acquisition process and the factors responsible for the changing dynamics of talent acquisition and management. Further it is attempted to analyse the influence of leadership, technology, culture and Quality of hire on job retention as well.

Objectives

- To understand the traditional and the modern disruptive talent acquisition and management process.
- To study the influence of modern factors on changing dynamics of talent acquisition and talent management
- To analyse the effect of Culture, Technology, Leadership and Quality of hire on Job retention.

Literature Review

As stated earlier talent acquisition is the procedure of identifying and acquiring skilled employees to meet necessities for the organizational requirements. Srivastava and Bhatnagar (2007) in their case study of Motorola in India, highlighted the impact of due diligence in talent acquisition which is the most crucial problem faced by the organizations in the present times. The practices which are used innovatively by one company become benchmark and soon they are followed by more or less every organization in the industry. But this is important for the organizations to keep their own goals and culture in mind, based upon which they should design their recruitment strategies. One strategy does not support every organization. E-recruiting and web functionalities had become collaborative approach in acquiring and managing talent. The online experience of web browser access, interactive interfaces, social networking, collaboration and community are now commonplace with candidates. Today, Internet users are old and young, male and female, skilled and unskilled. The use of the web for recruiting is no longer confined to professional and salaried positions. Increasingly it is also being used for recruiting for hourly jobs (Philips, 2008). Talent acquisition has evolved from a tactical, back-office process to a strategic endeavor that directly impacts organizational growth. Organizations struggling to identify and attract talent must rethink their current strategies and technology options in order to align with corporate objectives. A detailed survey was conducted with 234 organizations to explore how best-practice organizations build result driven talent acquisition programs, align goal with business objectives and to leverage world class technology to achieve results (Madeline Lauren 2013)

New Sources of Acquiring Talent

In past the process of recruitment was merely posting the openings on the career page of the organisation's website. This is no longer the right way of attracting the right candidate for the job. Companies are now finding unique ways of reaching out to newer talent and accessing the better talent pool using the disruptive technologies. Organisations are now treating recruitment as a drive for marketing their own self. Hence the partner with a corporate marketing firm and develop an integrated approach for attracting new talent. Facebook has no longer remained the only place where they can post job openings. Most of the organisations are going beyond it and leveraging the power of social media by building more robust and active communities over various other social media platforms like LinkedIn and twitter. In fact the focus has shifted to people and network of people who can become quality recruits.

Use big data to deepen talent networks: Organizations can now leverage big data tools from vendors such as Linked In, Face book, Talent Bin, Work4 and others to identify and source quality candidates around the world. Talent analytics will help in identifying the most important source of talent generation, this will help in determining the best fit that's will eventually improve the quality as well a efficiency of hiring. Few methods of acquiring and maintaining the quality of hire are by having an active strength of candidate resource so as to make sure in case of any emergency this repository can be utilized. The management of this resource is tricky they need to be constantly engaged so that they can be made into active mode from passive mode if need be. Another important platform is the social media that is a very big source of passive candidates. An aspirant can learn about his prospective employer by just joining the employer community. Table 1 summarizes the new sources of acquiring the talent.

Table 1 Sources of acquiring talent

Activity	Description
Boomerang Rehires	This rehire program is low cost, results in high ROI.
Shift from active tools	Companies need to look for passive job seekers who are too comfortable in their current organization as these are the considered to be the best talents according to the study conducted by Zinnov management Consulting. Capgemini has initiated the use of LinkedIn and Facebook for reaching out to passive seekers.
Mobile Technology	Mobile has transformed the way organisations operate. The Connectivity and opportunity have increased drastically and hence there must be provision for mobile solutions access to both recruiters and candidates.
Talent Acquisition Approach	360 degrees/720 degrees approach for enhancing excellence and empowerment.
Internal Promotion	Organizations must encourage internal promotions by providing employee with management development programs
Employer Branding	Various activities like CSR activities, campus connect activities and other innovative ways to source, develop and retain talent must be employed.
Assessment Centers	Having specific locations for assessing the hiring process.
Maintaining parity	Managing the balance between money and better learning in order to retain talent
Satellite Location Hiring	Having a common location near major cities will help in reaching the candidates who are not able to travel to big cities.
Diversity Hiring	Focus more on having a diversity among the workforce will ensure better workforce dynamics and efficiency.
Increasing focus on Employee Referrals	Referrals are cheaper, quick and better conversion rates in terms of joining the organization.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Statement of Problem

- Most organizations will find themselves competing to acquire high-performers. Hence the primary problem is to understand the existing talent acquisition and management process and the way it is getting disrupted.
- Success will depend on a combination of HR philosophy, how effectively they embrace the web, and how far they can drive through operational efficiencies, particularly in cutting costs and streamlining internal recruitment processes. There for the next research question is with respect to identifying the major factors influencing the present dynamic talent acquisition and management process.
- Based on the identified factors the study attempts to answer the question of the most influencing factor on the dependent variable (Job Retention)

Research Design

The study was aimed at evaluating the impact of culture, technology, leadership, quality of hire on job retention and engagement. Employees and employers working in corporate sector, government sector & self-employed constituted the population for the study. Purposive sampling technique was used to identify responses for the study and a sample size of 150 respondents was taken to conduct the study. Self-designed questionnaire was used for evaluating job retention and engagement of employees. Data was collected on a scale of, where 1 indicated strongly disagree and 5 indicated strongly agree. Cronbach's

Alpha reliability was computed using SPSS software to evaluate the reliability of the questionnaire.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 2: Frequency Distribution

Serial No	Questions	Mean	Standard Deviation
On the basis of Culture			
1	The organization has a positive value system that people understand and believe in.	4.072917	0.797955
2	I believe that I am accepted as part of the team in the organization.	4.312500	0.744276
3	People in the organization have the opportunity to be involved in the decision making process.	3.895833	0.911669
4	I believe the organization is open to change.	3.906250	1.016476
5	People in organization widely share the same philosophy.	3.604167	0.956740
6	I believe the organization offers sufficient job training for employees.	3.843750	0.998189
7	People in organization share a common set of moral principles.	3.708333	1.014803
8	I am pleased with the opportunities I have to be promoted in the organization	3.822917	0.870509
9	Company does its fair share to support community projects.	3.770833	0.839538
10	Management values the employees of organization.	3.875000	0.861455
11	Employee's capabilities are fully utilized.	3.947917	0.921895
12	Employees are recognized for good work	3.895833	0.934476
Technology			
1	Recruiters/HR generalists sharing valuable content about the "Brand" i.e. Its culture, values, mission, goals, benefits, training, etc. on social media.	3.968750	0.787443
2	Showcasing the firm's opportunities on the firms careerspage in websites, Face book page about the status updates	3.906250	0.834495
3	Technology used in promoting and strengthening the brand in the market place	3.927083	0.729019
4	Educate workforce on new and upcoming tools, techniques, practices and open source solutions	3.989583	0.760814
5	Develop depth in niche areas like embedded software, Bluetooth, security, chip development etc.	3.916667	0.902239
6	Set up small, independent and agile innovation centers focusing on new products and technology	3.916667	0.866532
Leadership			
1	When assigning tasks, I consider people's skills and interests.	4.460000	0.613122
2	I expect nothing less than top-notch results from people.	3.700000	0.994885
3	I expect my people to work harder than I do.	3.420000	1.341489
4	When someone is upset, I try to understand how he or she is feeling.	4.700000	0.505076
5	When circumstances change, I can struggle to know what to do	4.120000	0.824126
6	I think that personal feelings shouldn't be allowed to get in the way of performance and productivity.	3.980000	1.115567

7	My actions show people what I want from them.	4.000000	0.857143
8	When working with a team, I encourage everyone to work toward the same overall objectives.	4.540000	0.613122
9	I make exceptions to my rules and expectations – it's easier than being the enforcer all the time.	3.840000	0.888934

10	I make time to learn what people need from me, so that they can be successful.	4.500000	0.614452
Quality of Hire			
1	What are your organization biggest recruiting challenges?		
a)	Do you feel finding good candidates are difficult?	3.280000	1.125584
b)	Do you think filling positions fast is challenging?	3.580000	1.011969
c)	Is it difficult to Contact candidates?	2.860000	1.195399
d)	Do you find difficulty in scheduling interviews?	2.780000	1.200170
e)	Is sourcing resumes stressful?	3.200000	1.106567
2	Do you consider the reference check as an integral part of recruitment?	3.840000	1.113186
3	Do you consistently appoint high calibre employees?	3.560000	0.951047
4	Do you ensure that vacancies do not remain open for long period of time?	3.640000	1.208136
5	Are all company interviewers trained to sell our employer brand?	3.440000	1.231558
Job Retention			
1	Is talent acquisition truly working with other corporate departments in delivering the employer branding?	3.840000	0.976458
2	Are we working with our in-house employee groups to improve our candidate experience and on-boarding programs?	3.760000	1.060612
3	Do you believe that transfer, demotion, suspension and dismissal are based on performance appraisals?	3.520000	1.182181
4	Is your company lacking, fairness in supervision and inconsistency in employment opportunities, having an impact on employee retention?	3.460000	1.146601
5	Do you believe that cash incentives have more of the contribution in employee retention activity?	4.140000	0.926041

Culture: From the above table 2 we can interpret that Mean contributes **46.6562** on the scale of 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest and Standard deviation contributes **10.867981** to the culture of the organisation.

Technology: From the above table 2 we can interpret that Mean contributes **23.625** on the scale of 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest and Standard deviation contributes **4.880542** to the technology of the organisation.

Leadership: From the above table 2 we can interpret that Mean contributes **41.26** on the scale of 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest and Standard deviation contributes **8.3679** to the leadership of the organisation.

Quality of hire: From the above table 2 we can interpret that Mean contributes **30.18** on the scale of 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest and Standard deviation contributes **10.1436** to the quality of hire of the organisation.

Job retention and engagement: From the above table 2 we can interpret that Mean contributes **18.72** on the scale of 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest and Standard deviation contributes **5.2918** to the job retention and engagement of the organisation.

Factor Analysis

Kaiser - Meyer - Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity (KMO):

The Kaiser - Meyer - Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy value was 0.783 indicating that the sample was adequate to consider the data as normally distributed. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity tests the null hypothesis that the item-to-item correlation matrix was an identity matrix. The hypothesis was tested through Chi-Square test; the value of Chi-square was found to be 2172.554, which is significant at 1 per cent level of significance. Therefore, null hypothesis is rejected; indicating that the item-to-item correlation matrix is not an identity matrix and is therefore suitable for factor analysis as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.783
Bartlett's Test of Approx. Chi-Sphericity	2172.554
df	861
Sig.	.000

RELIABILITY TEST

Cronbach's Alpha reliability method was applied to check the reliability of all items in the employee and employer questionnaire. The reliability coefficient value was well within the required range which depicts high reliability of the questionnaire. Reliability test was applied using SPSS software and the reliability test measures are given below in table 5:

Table 4 Reliability Scores

Sl. No.	Construct	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
1	Culture (C1)	12	0.907
2	Technology (T1)	6	0.843
3	Leadership (L1)	10	0.724
4	Quality of Hire (Q1)	9	0.836
5	Job Retention (J1)	5	0.729

Testing Of Hypothesis Findings and Results

It is assumed that the Talent acquisition is influenced by various factors To find the influence of various factors on job retention regression analysis was carried out. Regressions analysis is conducted in order to identify the combined effect of all the factors (Independent variables/ predictors) on the outcome variable (dependent variable). The predictor variables are added using the enter method to the proposed model. T statistics are used for determine the significance of the predictor variables on outcome variables.

Ho: There is no significance influence of Culture (C1), technology (T1), Quality of hire (Q1) and leadership (L1) on Job Retention (J1)

To examine this relationship linear regression is carried out using SPSS 21 and the values R2 and Adjusted R2, Unstandardized β and corresponding significance levels are noted down for ascertaining the proposed model.

Regression

Table 5 Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.377 ^a	.142	.104	.62107

a. Predictors: (Constant), Q1, T1, L1, C1

Table 6 ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	5.806	4	1.451	3.763	.007 ^b
Residual	35.101	91	.386		
Total	40.906	95			

a. Dependent Variable: J1

b. Predictors: (Constant), Q1, T1, L1, C1

Table 7 Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.188	.767		2.854	.005
C1	.171	.138	.167	1.243	.217
T1	-.181	.144	-.168	-1.259	.211
L1	.137	.171	.081	.804	.424
Q1	.308	.095	.324	3.232	.002

a. Dependent Variable: J1

Findings

From the above analysis we have estimated mean and standard deviation from frequency distribution, communality test, and the KMO test tell that the sample is adequate

From the regression analysis it is evident that model is able to predict 37.3 percent of total variances shown in table 6. From the Anova table 7 the proposed model was found to be significantly able to predict the proposed job retention model as $p < 0.05$. Which lead to rejection of null hypothesis and acceptance of alternative hypothesis that there is a significance influence of factors on job retention.

On further evaluation of coefficients table 8, it is evident that of the four factors that were taken as predictor variables only quality of hire is significantly contributing to the model (Unstandardized $\beta = 0.308$, Sig = 0.002; $p < 0.05$). This implies that the hiring process is very important and organizations must develop robust processes in order to identify the right source and right target candidate. With the appearance of new trends and the opening of new tools, the talent acquisition process is continuously evolving. Its future sits on technology and third parties like consulting practices, search firms, recruitment process outsourcing, and more.

Implications of Talent Acquisition and Management

Hence the study highlights the most important factors influencing the talent acquisition and management is quality of hire. The recommendations are hence very clear that the organisations must find creative and innovative ways to identify the right source and reach right target candidates. Identify clearly the available resources and missing skills needed to compliment the current competencies and plan the recruitment process accordingly. It is very important to decode these traits in order to reach the right requirements of the workforce. Market of job requirements must be done in creative way so that it reaches the right candidates with right skills. Create a widespread referral network as these can help in getting the most suitable workforce for the specific jobs which will also save lot of time and money. Recent hired employees, collaborations with the organisations, candidates who are no longer a part of the company are all the prospective point of contact for strong referral network. Attach rewards, referral programs, redemptions prizes, cash awards as incentives that can be rolled out in case of successful referrals. Revamp the application process, decrease your workload and discover the accurate people for open positions quickly allowing interested job seekers to create a 'profile' of themselves. Additional information can be gathered which is specific to company's hiring objectives, and turn the workload in company's favor by not having to answer to every individual application. This way, the talent pool can be built exponentially and organisations can have a ready source to always for existing and upcoming position openings.

Conclusion

Major challenge in today's talent acquisition and management process is global abundance of candidates but scarce local talent. More number of older employees and less younger employees also makes it difficult for the organisations to plan for future as most of the employees are nearing retirement age. Diversity of workforce and workplace which makes it difficult for managers to manage all of them at once. Technology is proving to be major enabler for effectively managing talent. This will henceforth be more dependent on supply chain management principles as based on the requirements generated by the system the hiring process can be carried out. Talent Acquisition will also see a major change as these process will now be automated and probably outsourced to third party in order to reduce cost and time involved.

Functions like payroll are already being done away with. Since talent acquisition is an important and key business activity for most of the organisations the HR functions will have to derive long term strategic plans to actually benefit from it. The overall profitability of the organisations will and its corporate success will depend on it.

Scope for future research:

Future scope of work may be focused on understanding the new theories that will impact job retention and how these insights can help in development of talent management. New evolving models talent acquisition and management and its impact on global diversity will also contribute to good study. The individual, organizational and macro-contextual hindrances in managing and acquiring the talent and ways to overcome it will also be important piece of study. Impact of such developments on international business and the management of the same will need to be studied in detail. Roles and responsibilities of corporate, educational stakeholders and governments in improving the talent acquisition and management process will also be a good scope of future study.

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